

Cyclopic

Reimagining the wheel -
mechanical engineering meets AI

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Cyclopic is a UK-based autonomous mobility startup. Their modular EV platform could have a huge impact on society: helping people get around towns and cities, assisting in warehouses, handling 'last mile' deliveries, or even exploring other planets. At its heart is a patented centreless wheel that offers enhanced manoeuvrability and stability.

Cyclopic's unique EV platform has four integrated drive units, each connected to an independently acting centreless wheel to provide drive, steering, suspension and braking. Each drive unit is autonomous, with all software housed directly within the drive system. With integrated AI, the platform could be used as a logistics and delivery robot, an autonomous transportation pod, or even a multi-purpose unmanned aerial vehicle.

Through BridgeAI, the Cyclopic team carried out a feasibility study for an autonomous mobile robot (AMR) for warehouses. This demonstrated that advanced AI can work with Cyclopic's mechanical levelling system to provide automated balancing. Existing AMRs operating in tight, busy spaces have issues with stability, versatility, manoeuvrability and speed, and struggle to cope with slopes and obstacles. Cyclopic's advanced electric drive system offers much greater precision.

The Cyclopic team has been working with BridgeAI Independent Scientific Advisor Professor Hongkai Wen, who has helped them network with potential partners in academia and industry – including leading researchers at the Universities of Surrey, Warwick and Oxford. Professor Wen is helping them to explore new applications for the technology, providing technical guidance in areas such as adapting existing autonomous mobility algorithms to Cyclopic's system, and refining a digital twin that can test algorithms in a controlled virtual environment.

“Once we developed the platform from a mechanical engineering perspective, it was clear that we needed to integrate AI to make it autonomous and allow it to reach its full potential. We have been helped enormously by Innovate UK initiatives – including BridgeAI – that help small businesses progress along their AI adoption journey. That’s how the ISA programme came onto our radar, and we were delighted to be chosen to take part and matched with Hongkai.”

Carol Rallings
Co-Founder, Cyclopic

A proposed partnership with Coventry City Council could see Cyclopic’s autonomous pods helping people with mobility issues to get around the city. The Cyclopic team is seeking additional partners – investors, research collaborators and organisations that can make use of the technology – and is continuing to work towards commercialising its products.

“I believe Cyclopic’s innovative technology can have a transformative impact in its sector, with many downstream applications – particularly with the integration of AI and machine learning. It has been super exciting to learn about Cyclopic’s technology and the business side of things in my capacity as ISA, and even more rewarding to be able to contribute my expertise to its development through AI adoption.”

Professor Hongkai Wen
Chair in Machine Learning Systems, University of Warwick

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